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PIM KINASE: A SAVIOUR TO CAST OUT CARCINOMA

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ABSTRACT

PIM Kinase is indeed a serine/threonine protein that is discovered to be overexpressed and functions as an oncoprotein in a range of cancers. PIM-1, PIM-2, and PIM-3 are the three members of the PIM kinase family, and they have strikingly similar functions. They are mainly accountable for the regulation of the cell cycle, controlling anti-apoptotic activity, mediating the destruction of bones, etc. PIM kinase is concerned with downstream physiological events by phosphorylating cellular substrates like HP1, NFATc1, p21^{WAF1/CIP1}, p100, etc. Recent research has identified PIM kinase as a clinical indicator and potential therapeutic candidate for the tailored treatment of advanced cancer. The results of the current review provide insight into the function of PIM protein as pilot oncogenes in tumorigenesis and their applicability as therapeutic targets.

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INTRODUCTION

In solid and hematological cancers, oncogenic kinases regulate intercellular signaling cascades that regulate the development and survival of tumor cells. These kinases' activity is tightly controlled in healthy cells, but prolonged activation causes apoptosis resistance and uncontrolled cell proliferation. Serine/threonine enzyme PIM Kinase is frequently involved in human malignancies. It activates pathways that control a variety of physiological processes through the phosphorylation of substrates, which ultimately establishes the balance between cell survival and apoptosis.[1] The three enzymes that make up the PIM family of serine/threonine-specific kinases are PIM-1, PIM-2, and PIM-3.[2] The proviral insertion in murine (PIM) cancer related proteins, which comprise three serine/threonine kinase isoforms, are used by the Moloney murine leukemia virus to transmit itself.[3] Murine leukemia virus from Moloney is a convectional retrovirus that can be used to study leukemogenesis.[4]

There are many similarities between the amino acid sequences of the PIM isoforms, which are expressed by different genes on different human chromosomes. PIM-1 and PIM-2 carry 61% of these similarities, whereas the PIM-1 and PIM-3 connect 71%.[5] By mapping the retroviral assimilation sites in MMLV-induced lymphomas, PIM-1 was detected because more than 50% of T-cell lymphomas integrate close to the PIM locus, which results in higher quantities of PIM-1 mRNA.[6] Further research revealed that PIM-1 overexpressing T cells in transgenic mice made them more susceptible to chemically produced T-cell lymphomas.[7] Intriguingly, the compensatory expression of PIM-2 in reaction to the loss of PIM-1 was discovered by MMLV proviral insertion replicating in c-myc knockout mice lacking PIM-1.[8] Eventually, proviral tagging in c-myc transgenic mice results in the compensation activation of PIM-3 in these mice.[9] Six exons make up the PIM genes, and these exons result in mRNA transcripts that encode various PIM protein isoforms with various molecular weights, all of which retain their serine/threonine kinase activity.[10] PIM kinase is extensively present in the spleen, thymus, foetal liver, bone marrow, prostate, oral epithelia, lymph nodes, and hippocampus.[11]

The PIM-1 cDNA sequence suggests that both mouse and human PIM-1 encode a protein with masses of 34 and 44 kDa both of which are homologous to protein kinases. Both the 44 kDa and 34 kDa PIM-1 isoforms are mostly cytoplasmic and have similar *in vitro* kinase activity, but their *in vivo* association states and half-lives are different.[12] Alternative initiation sites for PIM-2 have also been documented, producing three distinct proteins of 34, 37, and 40 kDa, in contrast, a single protein has been discovered from PIM-3 transcripts,[13] the slow-transforming Moloney leukemia virus, which causes gene expression by insertional mutagenesis, prefers to integrate at the murine PIM-1 gene. Clonal growth of PIM-1 transcriptionally epigenetic cells is related to virally caused T cell lymphomas.[14] Human homolog PIM-1 is located on chromosome 6p12-21.[15] Oncogenicity of PIM-1 in transgenic and retroviral models has been thoroughly recognized.[16] The oncogenic potential is modest on its own, but it works well with c-Myc, L-myc, N-myc, Bcl-2, and Gfi-1 to promote T-cell lymphomagenesis. [17,18]

Mechanism of action

JAK-STAT signaling pathway, which can be activated by members of the Interleukin-6 (IL-6) family, is principally accountable for regulating PIM lymphoma proteins.[19] One of the primary ways PIM kinases control both survival and apoptosis is through the Bcl-2 class members, that have both pro- and anti-apoptotic activity (BAD and BAX). BAD is phosphorylated at ser112 by PIM kinases, which enhances binding and retention in the cytoplasm and prevents BAD from sticking to BCL-2. This prevents apoptosis onset.[20]

Caspase 3 (CASP3) and CASP9 activation are also prevented by PIM kinases.[21] PIM kinases interact synergistically with MYC, a proto-oncogene and transcription factor with important roles in cell proliferation, differentiation, metabolism, and survival/apoptosis. Transgenic mice containing PIM-1 supplements with immunoglobulin enhancer sequences upstream ($E\mu$) and a proviral long terminal repeat (LTR) downstream resulted in enhanced PIM-1 protein expression in both B and T cells, and the emergence of spontaneous clonal T cell lymphomas, albeit infrequency and with a long latency.[10] The cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitors p21 and p27 are phosphorylated by the PIM kinases. Phosphorylated p21 is stabilized and moved to the cytoplasm to promote proliferation.[22] Contrarily, PIM phosphorylation of p27 results in 14-3-3 binding, its removal from the nucleus, and its destruction by proteasomes.[23]

The ubiquitin-mediated proteasomal breakdown process is inhibited by hypoxia, which stabilizes and activates PIM-1. PIM-1 expression under the influence hypoxia could serve as a mediator of solid carcinoma transformation, as higher PIM-1 expression only accelerates NIH3T3 cell change when hypoxia is present. The dominant negative PIM-1 enhances apoptosis and reduces tumor angiogenesis in a mice tumor model for pancreatic cancer xenograft. Studies have shown that PIM-1 is necessary for the development of solid tumors, indicating that PIM-1 may be a good option for the treatment of solid tumors.[21]

Activation and influence of PIM-1

The mammalian PIM kinases, in contrast to the many protein kinases, simply lack a regulator motif and, as a result, are not activated by phosphorylation. Instead, they possess a kinase domain that is extremely conserved. Therefore, after translation, they are expected to become constitutively active.[24] Levels of translation, translation efficiency, and proteasomal degradation control the activity of PIM kinases.[25] In terms of activity, it is both controlled in expression and stability. PIM-1 has a half-life of around 5 minutes in normal peripheral blood cells, whereas it is 20 minutes in the chronic myelogenous leukemia cell line K562.[26]

After various cytokines and growth stimuli attach to its receptor, JAK upregulates the STAT proteins, forcing them to enter the nucleus and function as signaling pathways for the PIM genes. The gamma interferon stimulating domains of the PIM-1 gene attach to STAT-3 and STAT-5, increasing PIM-1 expression.[27] The mechanism is further complicated by the fact that mRNA stability affects and determines the PIM kinases' activity.[28]

According to one study, Escherichia coli tyrosine kinase (ETK) can also phosphorylate PIM-1 at Tyr218 to increase PIM-1 activity.[29] Further research has revealed that PIM-1 attaches to Hsp90 and Hsp70 in tumor cells, and that this association shields it from degradation by the ubiquitin-proteasome cascade. Contrarily, attachment to Hsp70 is associated with the amplification of PIM-1.[30]

Downstream events

The PIM kinases have particular functions in the control of signal transmission and cell cycle progression. Also, they share some substrates with PI3-dependent kinases that control apoptosis and cellular metabolism. PIM and protein kinase B (PKB), also referred to as Akt, both directly inactivate the cytotoxic Bcl-2 protein BAD.[31] The Akt and PIM kinases influence the modulation of the NF- κ B transcription factor through stimulation of the serine-threonine kinase Cot, a potential member of the MAPKKK family. I κ B is degraded by proteasomes as a result of this process, and as a result, NF- κ B localizes to the nucleoplasm and activates a number of anti-apoptotic proteins.[32] The transcription element NFATc is another PIM-1 substrate.[33]

Purpose and objectives of PIM-1

Because they promote both proliferation and survival of cells, PIM kinases have an advantageous edge in cancer. They have been found to phosphorylate several proteins *in vitro*, including transcriptional repressors (HP1) [34], activators (NFATc1) [35] and co-activators (p100)[36], cell cycle regulators (p21^{WAF1/CIP1})[37], Cdc25A phosphatase[38] and the kinase C-TAK1/MARK3/Par1A, and co-activators (c-Myb).[39] PIM-1 kinase may interact physically with BAD *in vitro* and *in vivo*, phosphorylating it on Ser112 to act as a gatekeeper for deactivation. Additionally, PIM-1 can shield cytokine-de-defended FDCP1 cells from BAD-induced apoptosis, indicating that PIM-1's phosphorylation of BAD is necessary but probably not sufficient to improve cell survival following cytokine withdrawal.[40]

The PIM proteins' proven relevance in oncology is paralleled by their pro-survival activity in immunology. Whereby aberrant expression of these kinases has been associated with many human malignancies, including multiple myeloma [41], chronic lymphocytic leukemia [42], pancreatic cancer [43], and prostate cancer.[44] PIM-1 is essential for the growth of pulmonary arterial hypertension and neo-intima on the aortic wall, two vascular diseases linked to the growth of vascular endothelial cells. More research into PIM-1's role in high glucose-driven (HG) smooth-muscle vascular proliferation revealed that PIM-1 expression originally decreased in response to HG for a short period of time before gradually increasing both at the transcriptional and translational levels.[45] It has been demonstrated that hypoxia increases PIM-1 expression, which encourages the formation of solid tumors.[46] Anti-tumor medications occasionally cause stress, which improves tumor survival. For the anticancer medication docetaxel, a mechanism underpinning such a response has been identified.[47]

Recent research employing human vascular endothelium cells suggested that PIM kinases and c-MYC function in concert, possibly via PIM's phosphorylation of histone H3. PIM-1 appears to have an attraction to the MYC E-box parts, which produces a complex. This substance activates RNA polymerase II and a subgroup of MYC-dependent gene products via transcription by phosphorylating H3-S10.[48] PIM kinases serve as survival factors whenever both human and animal PIM cDNAs have been forcedly expressed in various cell lines. They do this by inhibiting apoptotic death of cells, which controls the balance between pro- and anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 family protein components.[49]

Structure-based understanding of PIM inhibition

PIM-1 also contains an insertion in the hinge region, which is required for ATP binding, and a proline residue at a critical point (position 123) in the protein. All three PIMs were able to interact with the natural substrate ATP because the carbonyl in the backbone of E121 and the adenine amino moiety formed a single hinge hydrogen bond. The hinge's P123 lacked the ability to join the nitrogen of the ATP adenine ring to a hydrogen bond donor, which is often present in other kinases.[50] Moreover, the hinge contained a V126 addition that other kinases lacked. The neighboring binding pocket grew larger due to the modified hinge configuration. These differences between PIMs and other kinases gave the option to create specific pan-PIM inhibitors. [51,52] While two lysine residues and two magnesium ions bind to ATP, two hydrogen bonds keep the hinge section in the active conformation. These ions then join with oxygen atoms on the Asx or Glx side chains. PIM-1 is unique from those other protein kinases because it contains a proline moiety at location 123. The usual additional hydrogen bond between the adenine group of ATPs and the hinge axis cannot form because P123 is unable to function as a hydrogen bond donor.[53]

The recent discovery of the PIM-1 molecular structure by numerous groups has increased the probability of developing PIM-1-selective inhibitors. An extra amino acid residue sets the hinge region, which houses the ATP binding site, apart from those of similar protein kinases. Because proline-123 lacks an essential amide H-bond donor, it is unable to chemically bind with ATP. This structural characteristic plays a significant role in determining how PIM inhibitors bind.[54]

Cellular components of PIM Kinase

Due to the functional redundancy of the PIM kinase family, they mediate their physiological functions by phosphorylating a broad range of cellular substrates, which considerably overlap. PIM-1 displays a considerable affinity for substrates that contain (K/R)3-X-S/T-X, where X is neither a basic nor a significant hydrophobic residue.[55] They share a lot of cellular substrates since the PIM substrate sequence and AKT's are quite similar.[25] According to data, PIM-1 and the Runt-related transcription factor (RUNX) family of regulatory proteins can physically interact, co-localize in nuclei, and undergo *in vitro* phosphorylation. Furthermore, Runx1 and probably other members of the RUNX family are potentiated by PIM-1 in terms of their transcriptional activity.[56].

It was discovered that heterochromatin protein 1 (HP1) functions as a PIM-1 binding protein, that PIM-1 phosphorylates HP1, and that the deletion of PIM-1's phosphorylation sites results in a partial loss of HP1's ability to suppress transcription.[57] It was discovered that (tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated factor 2/sorting nexin 6) TFAF2/SNX6 functions as a PIM-1 binding protein in addition to 5-(4-phenoxybutoxy) psoralen (PAP-1) and HP-1.[58] Also, Forkhead box O (FoxO) transcription factors are phosphorylated and rendered inactive by PIM, which suppresses p27Kip1 transcription. According to the data, PIM kinases control the transcriptional and post-transcriptional production of p27Kip1, which is necessary for cell proliferation and cell cycle progression.[23] PIM-1 boosts the phosphatase activity of the phosphatase Cdc25C both *in vivo* and *in vitro* by phosphorylating it. Research results significantly indicate the role of PIM-1 at the G2/M checkpoint through a variety of pathways.[59] PIM-1 also regulates mTOR function by phosphorylating PRAS40. Therefore, elevations in mTOR activity caused by PIM protein kinase may be able to control cell development. Cells overexpressing PIM-1 keep phosphorylating PRAS40 on Thr246 even when there are no growth stimuli present.[60]

Apoptosis signal-regulating kinase 1 (ASK1) is directly bound by PIM-1 and phosphorylated on Ser83. This PIM-1-mediated phosphorylation keeps the ASK1 kinase inactive, which lowers the amount of JNK and p38 downstream phosphorylation by ASK1 that takes place. PIM-1's regulation of ASK1 activity prevents caspase-3 from activating in response to stress, which lowers the rate of cell death. PIM-1 appears to promote cell survival since it inhibits that stress-induced ASK1-JNK/p38-caspase-3 apoptotic cascade physiologically.[61] PIM generally interacts with the p53 system, but when it is produced at pathological levels, it operates as a typical dominant oncogene that triggers the p53 pathway to provide a protective response.[62] PIM-1 kinase participates in the formation of the complex between NuMA, HP1, dynein, and dynactin, which is required for mitosis, most likely by phosphorylation.[63] Similar to this, PIM-1 overexpression causes cells with spindle anomalies to evade mitotic arrest and lose checkpoint control, which prevents them from completing the cell cycle and leads to multinucleation and polyploidy.[64]

PIM kinase for a focused cure

Due to their presence overexpressed in many cancers and their participation in a number of cancer-specific processes, such as cell growth, migrations, and localization, PIM kinases are interesting therapeutic targets. PIM-1 kinase was initially found to be overexpressed in leukemia and lymphoma tumors.[65] Nevertheless, more recently, it was discovered that PIM-1 was elevated in solid tumors, including liver, pancreatic, prostate, squamous cell, colorectal cancers [66] and liposarcoma.[67] PIM-1 kinase is linked to chemo-resistance in prostate cancer cells, which is a typical occurrence in more aggressive, hormone-refractory prostate tumors, according to recent investigations.[68] The fact that PIM-1-deficient mice are viable and only exhibit a modest impairment in hematopoiesis[69] demonstrates that PIM-1 helps hematopoietic cells develop and survive, while its function is likely secondary to that of other signaling pathways. More crucially, mice lacking PIM-1, PIM-2, and PIM-3 expression are nevertheless viable and fertile despite having much smaller bodies at birth and throughout postnatal life.[70]

When PIM-1 function is hindered by a dominant-negative mutant PIM-1 protein, cells become more prone to apoptosis driven due to glucose deprivation under hypoxia.[21] Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) cells with K-RAS mutations exhibit decreased invasion, xenograft growth, radio-resistance, and anchorage-independent and anchorage-dependent cell growth properties when PIM-1 is suppressed by shRNA in K-RAS-dependent PDAC cell lines.[71] The induction of sarcomas *in vivo* by 3-methylcholanthrene carcinogenic therapy was significantly suppressed by the absence of PIM kinase.[72]

PIM kinases may be crucial to the *in vivo* invasion of bone. PIM genes appear to function additively because the absence of the all the three PIM kinases inhibits bone invasion more effectively than just the silence of PIM-2 and PIM-3 individually. The absence of PIM kinases can inhibit bone invasion brought on by 3-methyl-cholanthrene-induced sarcomas.[72] Through modulation of CXCR4, PIM-1 activity is crucial for the homing and migration of hematopoietic cells. PIM-1 inhibitors may work to restrict interactions with the microenvironment in part to exercise their anticancer effects because CXCR4 also controls the homing and maintenance of cancer stem cells.[73] PIM-1 has the ability to phosphorylate NFATc1, but in contrast to all other reported NFATc kinases, it fails to stop NFATc1 from entering the nucleus. PIM-1, on the other hand, works in a manner that is downstream of Ras to promote NFAT-mediated transactivation and IL-2 synthesis in activated Jurkat T cells.[33] PIM-1 appears to be key to the control of non-homologous end-joining repair because its suppression increased the apoptotic cell death brought on by drugs like paclitaxel, which inhibit the ATM-dependent DNA repair pathway.[74]

Involvement of PIM kinase in cancer treatment

PIM kinases are implicated in cancer-specific pathways and are elevated in many malignancies, making them appealing therapeutic targets for the treatment of cancer.[75] Different tumor types have different amounts of expression for specific PIM members. PIM-1 is thought to play a role in mediating the anti-apoptotic effects of oncogenes like FLT3, JAK2, and BCR/ABL mutations. PIM-1 was initially identified as being upregulated in human lymphoid and myeloid leukemia.[76] Later research revealed that PIM-1 was elevated in solid tumors, such as liver cancer, squamous carcinoma, colorectal cancer, pancreatic cancer, prostate cancer, and other pancreatic diseases [77] and bladder carcinoma.[78] Identical outcomes were discovered for esophageal [79] and gastric cancer[80], wherein an infection with *H. pylori* raised PIM-1 in a cell culture model.[81] When head and neck cancer was more advanced, PIM-1 was highly expressed, and it was linked to lymph node metastasis and a bad prognosis.[82] In contrast to these outcomes, primary non-small-cell lung cancer was found to have a considerable downregulation of PIM-1 mRNA, PIM-1 levels were much lower in lymph node metastases than in nodal negative tumors.[83]

PIM-2 expression is extremely carcinogenic in hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), and its overexpression may cause the NF- κ B signaling pathway to be activated through an increase in phosphorylated RIPK2 levels.[84] It has been established that PIM-2-mediated aerobic glycolysis, in combination with mTORC1 signaling, is crucial for colon cancer cells.

PIM-2 is known to regulate glucose metabolism in tumor cells.[85] Additionally, it has been shown that PIM-2 expression is increased in bone marrow stromal cells, acting as an inhibitor of osteoblastogenesis. *In vivo*, PIM-2 inhibition stopped bone deterioration and the development of Multiple Myeloma tumors.[86] According to recent studies, PIM-2 kinase regulates the important glycolytic enzyme HK2's protein stability in cancer cells of the breast by phosphorylating it at Ser-473.[87] HSF1 is phosphorylated by PIM-2 at Thr-120, which increases its ability to bind to the PD-L1 locus and increase PD-L1 expression, both of which help breast cancer tumors develop.[88]

Since evidence suggests that PIM-1 as well as PIM-3 could phosphorylate a similar group of substrates, observations of PIM-1's biological actions may be able to shed light on PIM-3's role.[89]

Small molecule inhibitors of PIM kinase activity

In light of the considerable structural similarities between PIM kinase and other known serine/threonine kinases supported by the crystallographic studies currently available, it may be difficult to identify a selective inhibitor. [24,54] Additionally, the consensus hinge-region sequence shared by the PIM family kinases is especially distinctive because it contains two proline residues. This particular sequence may cause the configuration of this hinge region to vary from another kinase hinge regions.[90] Over 100 PIM inhibitors which have been divided into multiple different chemical families have recently been described, in either patents or academic articles.[91] Interestingly, even though PIM-1 is the target of most inhibitors, most of them inhibit all PIM kinases.[92] Due to the PIM family's redundancy, it may be more beneficial to simultaneously block all PIM kinases while treating cancer patients. Furthermore, as mice without all three PIM class components are healthy and productive and only minor deviations in hematopoietic growth responses could be identified, no major side events are expected despite this thorough PIM suppression.[70] PIM inhibitors also restored many chemotherapeutic medicines' sensitivity in resistant cell lines.[93]

Using the structure-based design, novel, powerful PIM inhibitors have been successfully discovered.[51] Over the years, numerous heterocyclic rings were synthesized in the lab, including derivatives of pyrrole[84], pyrimidine[94], thiazolidine[95], benzofuran[96], indole[97], triazole[98], oxadiazole[99], and quinoline.[100] These compounds are all linked to the PIM kinase inhibitory action by a particular ring or functional group. Clinical trials are now being conducted with several PIM kinase inhibitors, including FTI LGB321, SMI4a, AZD1208, CX-6258, INCB053914, LGH447, SEL24, TP-3654, etc. [101] The PIM kinase may be viewed as a useful target for the creation of new anticancer medications. There is also a strong argument for studying PIM inhibitors in conjunction with PI3K/AKT/mTOR and MAPK/ERK pathway inhibitors, as well as the possibility of combination with the existing standard of therapy in an effort to overcome resistance or refractoriness.[102]

CONCLUSIONS

Due to their crucial functions in malignancies, PIM kinases have received extensive research as a possible therapeutic target for creating anti-cancer medicines. Cellular activities and cell signaling pathways depend heavily on the PIM kinase. They act as a significant element that transmits a signal from various growth factors. *In vitro* studies have shown that they can phosphorylate a variety of proteins, including the transcriptional repressors HP1 and p100, the kinases C-TAK1/MARK3/Par1A, co-activators, and controllers of the cell cycle (p21WAF1/CIP1), (c-Myb). These signals later govern the growth, differentiation and survival of cells. The pro-survival action of PIM proteins in immunology parallels their established relevance in cancer. Since the compensatory mechanism exists between the members of the PIM family, inhibiting all the members rather than targeting a single isoform is a better treatment strategy. Whereby several human cancers, including hematological malignancies, chronic lymphocytic leukemia and prostate cancer, have been linked to abnormal expression of these kinases. The PIM kinase may be viewed as a useful target for the creation of new anticancer medications. Due to the presence of unique hinge regions in PIM kinases, they provide an opportunity to develop selective inhibitors with reduced toxicities. Even though PIM kinases are weak oncogenes, PIM kinase inhibitors can act as a probable target for anti-tumor treatment.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATIONS

PIM	- Proviral insertion in murine
TFAF2/SNX6	- Tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated factor 2/sorting nexin 6
MMLV	- Moloney murine leukemia virus
NF-κB	- Nuclear Factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells
IκB	- Nuclear factor of kappa light polypeptide gene enhancer in B-cells inhibitor
NFATc	- Nuclear component of activated T cells
Bcl-2	- B-cell lymphoma 2
JAK	- Janus Kinase
STAT	- Signal transducer and activator of transcription proteins
BAD	- Bcl-2 associated death promoter

BAX	- Bcl-2 Associated X-protein
ETK	- Escherichia coli tyrosine kinase
Hsp90	- Heat shock protein 90
PKB	- Protein kinase B
MAPKKK	- Mitogen-Activated Protein Kinase
HG	- High glucose
RUNX	- Runt-related transcription factor
HP1	- Heterochromatin protein 1
FoxO	- Forkhead box O
ASK1	- Apoptosis signal-regulating kinase 1
PDAC	- Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma

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